

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF ECZEMA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO VICHARCHIKA: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

In ayurveda all skin diseases come under classification of *Kushtha*. *Vicharchika* one of the *Kshudra Kushtha* characterized by *Kandu* (itching), *Raga* (redness), *Pidaka* (vesicular eruptions), *Vaivarnyata* (blackish discoloration) and *Bahustrava* (discharge may be watery or mixed with blood) with *Kapha-Pitta* dominance. It can be correlated with eczema. In this case report a 18-year-old female patient presented with complaints of *Daha* (burning sensation), *Kandu*, *Strava* and *Vaivarnyata* (blackish discoloration) over extensor surface of bilateral upper and lower limbs. The case was diagnosed as *Vicharchika* based on Ayurvedic parameters and eczema on modern background. There was significant improvement noted in signs and symptoms treated with *Virechana Karma* and some oral and external Ayurvedic medications.

KEYWORDS: Eczema, *Vicharchika*, *Virechana Karma*, *Kushtha*, case report.

INTRODUCTION

The skin is the body's largest sensory organ and serves as a protective barrier. It shields the body from various organisms, chemicals and antigens. Skin diseases are common worldwide, with a higher prevalence among children and individuals from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, often due to inadequate hygiene.^[1] Eczema, also known as atopic dermatitis, is

a common chronic skin condition that causes dry, itchy, inflamed skin; redness; rash; in some case flaking, blistering, cracking, oozing or bleeding. It can affect people of all ages but is especially common in children. Eczema is not contagious, but it can be uncomfortable and impact quality of life. Common triggering factors includes soaps, detergents, allergens, weather changes, stress, and certain fabrics. In modern medicine, there is no specific treatment for eczema, it can be managed with moisturizers, topical corticosteroids, avoiding triggers, and in and in some cases, oral medications or immunotherapy.^[2] In Ayurveda, all skin disorders are categorized under the term *Kustharoga*. These are further divided into two main types: *Mahakushtha* and *Kshudrakushtha*, which are classified into seven and eleven subtypes, respectively.^[3] *Kustharoga* is also recognized as one of the *Asta Mahagada*—the eight major diseases in Ayurveda.^[4] According to Ayurveda *Vicharchika* can be correlated to eczema one of the *Kshudra Kushtha* described in Brihatrayis. *Vicharchika* is characterized by *Sakandu pidaka*, *shyava* (Blackish), *Bahusrava* (oozing).^[5] It is *Rakta Pradoshaja Vikara* being involved of three Dosha with dominance of *Kapha*. It is *Rakta Pradoshaja Vikara* being involved of three *Dosha* with dominance of *Kapha*.^[6]

CASE STUDY

A female patient of 18 years old with MRD number 6558048 came in Kayachikitsa OPD Institute of medical science BHU Sir Sundarlal Hospital with complaints of reddish dark patches over bilateral legs and forearms over extensor surface characterized by *Kandu* (itching), *Rookshata* (dryness of skin), *Daha*(burning sensation) and *trava* (watery discharge and occasionally bleeding) since 2 years.

HISTORY OF PRESENT ILLNESS

Patient was apparently asymptomatic before 2 years after that she had complaint of intense itching over bilateral legs and forearms associated with scaling and watery discharge and occasionally bleeding. The symptoms are of gradual in onset with progressive in nature. Patient feels dryness initially at affected site followed by itching, redness and watery discharge and bleeding. Hence patient came to Kayachikitsa OPD Sir Sundarlal Hospital IMS BHU for Ayurveda management.

PAST HISTORY

No history of Diabetes mellitus type II/ Hypertension/Thyroid dysfunction.

FAMILY HISTORY

Patient's father had same complaints of skin.

PERSONAL HISTORY

Diet - vegetarian 2 to 3 meals per day

Bowel - 1 time daily with normal consistency

Micturition - 5 to 6 times per day

Occupation – Student

Addiction - Not any

GENERAL EXAMINATION

BP – 116/70mmHg, pulse rate – 80/min, respiratory rate – 15/min

Built is moderate, on skin examination there were blackish red pigmentation below knee with itching, burning sensation, cracking of skin, watery discharge and mild bleeding. Nutrition was good. Pallor, cyanosis, clubbing, icterus, oedema was absent and lymph nodes were not palpable.

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

C.V.S – S1 & S2 normally heard; no murmur present.

R.S – Trachea centrally placed; uniform chest expansion; bilaterally equal air entry.

G.I.T – Soft, no scar, no pigmentation, non-tender, no organomegaly.

C.N.S – The patient is well oriented to person, place and time.

ASHTAVIDHA PAREEKSHA

- *Nadi - Vata Kapha*
- *Mutra -4 -5 times a day, 1 time at night*
- *Mala – Samyaka*
- *Jivha – Nirama*
- *Shabda – Spashta*
- *Sparsha – Anushna*
- *Drika – Prakrita*
- *Akriti - Madhyama*

Table 1: Gradation of Symptoms/Subjective Parameters of Vicharchika*

Symptoms	Gradation	Score	BT	1st FU	2nd FU
<i>Kandu</i> (Itching)	No itching	0	2	1	0
	Itching present rarely	1			
	Itching disturbing patient's attention	2			
	Severe itching disturbing patients sleep	3			
<i>Strava</i> (Discharge)	No <i>Strava</i>	0	2	1	0
	Occasional <i>Strava</i> after itching	1			
	Mild <i>Strava</i> after itching	2			
	Profuse <i>Strava</i> making clothes wet	3			
<i>Pidaka</i> (Papules)	Absent	0	3	3	0
	1-2 <i>Pidaka</i> in one affected part	1			
	3-4 <i>Pidaka</i> in one affected part	2			
	More than 4 <i>Pidaka</i> in one affected part	3			
<i>Shyavata/ Vaivarnyata</i> (Discoloration)	Normal skin colour	0	2	1	0
	Brownish red discoloration	1			
	Blackish red discoloration	2			
	Blackish discoloration	3			
<i>Rookshata</i> (Dryness)	No dryness	0	3	2	1
	Dryness with rough skin	1			
	Dryness with scaling	2			
	Dryness with cracking	3			
<i>Daha</i> (Burning Sensation)	Absence of burning sensation in affected part	0	2	1	0
	Rarely burning sensation in affected part	1			
	Continuous burning sensation in affected part	2			
	Disturbing patients sleep	3			

TREATMENT

The patient was advised for *Virechana Karma* and oral medication along with external applications of medication. The details of therapy are as described as follow.

VIRECHANA KARMA

After *Deepana Paachana*, *Snehapana* was started with *Panchatikta Ghrita* with initial dose of 30 ml, gradually dose was increased by 30 ml upto 210ml on 7th day of *Snehapana*. On 7th day, *Snehapana* of 210 ml of *Ghrita*, patient was presented with *Samyaka Snehapana Lakshanas* like *Vata-Anulomana*, *Deepta- agni* (digestive fire becomes stronger) *Snigdha Varchaha* (faeces becomes oily, loose and smooth) and *Snigdhangata* (skin becomes unctuousness). From next day, *Sarvang Abhyanga* with coconut oil followed by *Bashpa Swedana* for 3 days. On third day of *Swedana*, after *Swedana Virechana Aushadhi* Trivrutta

Avleha 80gm along with lukewarm water was given. There was total 15 *Virechana Vega* with *Madhyama Shuddhi*. Patient was advised for *Sansarjana Krama* of 5 days.

SANSHAMAN CHIKITSA Table 2

Sanshaman chikitsa was started after completion of *Sansarjana Karma*. It includes following medicines.

Sr. No.	Date	Symptoms	Treatment given
1.	03/03/2024	Patient visited in OPD with above mentioned symptoms and got planned for <i>Virechana Karma</i> .	<i>Deepana Paachana, Snehapana</i> and <i>Abhyanga Virechana</i> by <i>Trivritta Avleha</i> 80 gm
2.	22/03/2024	Reddish dark patches over bilateral lower limbs with itching, flaking, burning sensation and mild blood oozing Dryness of skin	1.Tab. <i>Gandhak Rasayana</i> 250mg twice daily 2. Tab. <i>Kaishore Guggulu</i> 250mg thrice daily 3. Tab. <i>Panchatikta Ghrita Guggulu</i> 250mg thrice daily 4. <i>Patolkaturohinyadi Kashaya</i> 20ml twice daily with lukewarm water 5. <i>Prakshalana</i> with <i>Triphala Kwath</i> plus <i>Amaltas Patra</i> followed by local application of <i>Naalpamaradi Ker oil</i>
3.	05/04/2024	Reddish dark patches over bilateral limbs with itching and watery discharge.	1.Tab. <i>Gandhak Rasayana</i> 250mg + <i>Guduchi Satva</i> 250mg + <i>Vyadhiharana Rasa</i> 125mg twice daily 2. Tab. <i>Kaishore Guggulu</i> 500mg twice daily 3. <i>Patolkaturohinyadi Kashaya</i> 20ml twice daily with lukewarm water 4.Tab <i>Krimikuthar Rasa</i> 250 mg twice daily 5. <i>Prakshalana</i> with <i>Triphala Kwath</i> plus <i>Amaltas Patra</i> followed by local application of <i>Naalpamaradi Ker oil</i>
4.	10/05/2024	Significant improvement in symptoms of itching, watery discharge with reduction in all symptoms.	1.Tab. <i>Gandhak Rasayana</i> 250mg + <i>Guduchi Satva</i> 250mg + <i>Vyadhiharana Rasa</i> 125mg twice daily 2. Tab. <i>Kaishore Guggulu</i> 500mg twice daily 3. <i>Patolkaturohinyadi Kashaya</i> 20ml twice daily with lukewarm water 4. <i>Prakshalana</i> with <i>Triphala Kwath</i> plus <i>Amaltas Patra</i> followed by local application of <i>Naalpamaradi Ker oil</i>

DISCUSSION

VIRECHANA KARMA

The present case study shows symptoms of *Kshudra Kushtha Vicharchika* having *Kapha Pitta* dominance. *Virechana* is therapy by which there is pacification of these two *Doshas* along with *Vata anulomana, Srotoshodhana*, thus reducing burning sensation, itching.^[7]

Gandhak Rasayana is polyherbal drug which is *Rakta Shodhaka* (blood purifier), *Kandughana* and *Rasayana* mainly indicated in *Kushtha Roga*. *Sudha Gandhak* (purified

Sulphur), *Twak* (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum*), *Ela* (Cardamom), *Patra* (*Cinnamomum tamala*), *Nagkeshara* (*Mesua ferrea*), *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula*), *Amalaki* (*Emblica officinalis*), *Vibhitaki* (*Terminalia bellerica*), *Shunthi* (*Gingiber officinalis*), *Bhrigaraaja* (*Eclipta alba*), *Sita Mishri* (sugar). It has been prepared by giving twelve *Bhavanas* each of *Kwath* of *Chaturjata* (combination of four ayurvedic drugs – Cinnamon, Cardamon, Indian bay leaf and *Nagkeshara*) *Triphala* (combination of three herbs – *Amalaki*, *Haritaki* and *Bibhitaki*), *Shunthi* and *Swarasas* of *Guduchi*, *Bhringraj*, *Adraka* with pure *Gandhaka*. It is *Rakta Shodhaka* (blood purifier), *Kandughana* (anti-itching property) and *Rasayana* (*Rejuvenation therapy*) mainly indicated in *Kushtha Roga*. *Gandhaka Rasayana* is known to correct skin discoloration, thereby aiding in the restoration of the skin's natural tone. Additionally, it works to pacify *Dooshita Kapha* and detoxify the body by neutralizing *Visha* (toxins).^[8]

Kaishor guggulu contains *Triphala*, *Guduchi*, *Trikatu*, *Trivrutta*, *Danti*, *Vidanga* and *Ghrit*. It is *Raktaprasadana* (Blood -Purifier), *Strotoshodhana* (Body- Channels purification) and *Malanulomaka* (Laxation).^[9]

Panchatikta Ghrit Guggulu contents having *Tikta Rasa*, *Laghu* and *Ruksha Guna* so it acts as anti-itching property, *Kleda* and *Vikrut Meda Upshoshan*, *Vranashodhak*.^[10]

Patolkaturohinyadi Kashaya is described in *Ashtang Hriday*. *Nitya Virechana* was given that helps in correcting *Jatharagni* and *Dhatvagni* which is necessary to eliminate *Ama Dosha* and *Dushit Doshas* with its *Rechana* property. It contains *Patola*, *Katurohini*, *Chandana*, *Madhusrava*, *Guduchi* and *Patha*. This herbal preparation has *Kaphapittashaman* property, also detoxify being laxative, thereby reducing *Daha*, *Kandu*.^[11]

Krimikuthar Rasa-It is an important herbo-mineral formulation which contains *Karpura*, *Kutaja*, *Trayamana*, *Ajamoda*, *Vidanga*, *Hingula Bhasma*, *Vatsanabha*, *Palasha Beeja*. It is specially indicated in *Krimi Janya Tvak Vikara*. These *Sankramika Vyadhi* spreads from person to person by *Krimi* through *Sweda* also. Hence this is one of the reasons it is selected for this study *Sankramika* or *Aupasargika Roga Nidana* of *Kustha* is explained by Acharya Sushrut and *Vicharchika* is one of the *KshudraKushtha*.^[12]

Guduchi have anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, immunomodulatory, antimicrobial properties. In Ayurveda it is said to be *Rasayana* and *Vranaropak* properties.^[13]

Vyadhiharana Rasa - It contains *Trikatu* (*Pippali*, *Maricha*, *Shunthi*), *Hing* (asafoetida), *Trilavana* (three kinds of salt) and *Vatsanabha* (purified *Aconitum ferox*) processed in sesame oil and *Surdrava* (honey or alcohol). *Vyadhiharan Rasa* literally means “Disease-removing formulation.” It is *Deepana* (appetizer), *Pachana* (digestive), and *Krimighna* (anti-parasitic). *Vatsanabha*, a powerful *Vata-Kapha* pacifying agent (when purified properly). *Trikatu* and *Hing* stimulate *Agni* (digestive fire) and relieve *Ama* (toxins). It is indicated in *Ajeerna*, *Kushtha* and *Krimiroga*. It is *Raktashodhak* and *Shothahara* property on *Twak* and *Snayu*.^[14]

Vrana Prakshalana - *Triphala Kwath* quantity sufficient with *Churna* and water in 1:4 ratio boiled until it becomes one fourth. The *Kwath* is left for cooling until it becomes lukewarm. The hyperpigmented areas were washed with this *Kwath* followed by local application of *Naalpamaradi tail*.

RESULT

Patient had started improving during treatment and show significant improvement in all subjective and objective parameters after 60 days of treatment.

1. Lesions were completely resolved.
2. Relief in symptoms like itching, burning sensation, redness and dryness.
3. No recurrence of symptoms after treatment according to patient through telephonic communication.

Figure 1 – Before and after treatment lesion over left foot

Figure 2 – Before and after treatment lesion over right leg

Figure 3 – Before and after treatment lesion over arms

Figure 1: Before treatment and after treatment lesion over left foot.

Figure 2: Before and after treatment lesion over right leg.

Figure 3: Before and after treatment lesion over arms.

CONCLUSION

Eczema which can be correlated to *Vicharchika* in Ayurveda, as per references available in Ayurvedic literature and *Dosha Dushya* in present case the combined use of *Virechana Karma* along with *Shamana Aushadhi* and external application of *Kwatha* showed the significant improvement in symptoms like *Kandu*, *Raga*, *Srava* and *Pidaka*. To see the changes at molecular level needs further research.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST – None.

REFERENCES

1. Bos JD, Zonneveld I, Das PK, Krieg SR, van der Loos CM, Kapsenberg ML. The skin immune system (SIS): distribution and Immunopheno type of lymphocyte subpopulations in normal human skin. *J Invest Dermatol*, 1987; 88(5): 569-573.
2. Ralston SH, Penman ID, Strachan MWJ, Hobson RP, editors. *Davidson's Principles and Practice of Medicine*. 24th ed. Elsevier, 2022; 1223–1224.
3. Agnivesha. Charaka Samhita (Chikitsa Sthana), Tṛtīya Bhāga. 4th ed. Late Dr.laxmidhar Dwivedi, Dr. B.K. Dwivedi, Dr. P. K. Goswami, editors. Chaukhamba Prakashan Varanasi, 2023; 7/13.
4. Agnivesha. Charaka Samhita (Indriya Sthana), Tṛtīya Bhāga. 4th ed. Late Dr.laxmidhar Dwivedi, Dr. B.K. Dwivedi, Dr. P. K. Goswami, editors. Chaukhamba Prakashan Varanasi, 2023.
5. Agnivesha. Charaka Samhita (Chikitsa Sthana), Tṛtīya Bhāga. 4th ed. Late Dr.laxmidhar Dwivedi, Dr. B.K. Dwivedi, Dr. P. K. Goswami, editors. Chaukhamba Prakashan Varanasi, 2023; 7/26
6. Agnivesha. Charaka Samhita (Sutra Sthana), Tṛtīya Bhāga. 4th ed. Late Dr.laxmidhar Dwivedi, Dr. B.K. Dwivedi, Dr. P. K. Goswami, editors. Chaukhamba Prakashan Varanasi, 2023; 28/11.
7. Pallavi Bhagwat Rathod, Seema D. Bahatkar, Virechana Karma in Eczema (Kshudra Kushtha): A Case Study. *J Ayu Int Med Sci*, 2022; 7(10): 276-279.
8. Prof. Shriram S.Savrikar, Sharangadahara Samhita of sarangadhar, translated into English. Madhyama khanda 6/15, churna Kalpana, Chaukambha sanskrit pratishthan, Delhi, vol- 2; 1st edition, 2020; pg.179.
9. Sharangadhara. *Sharangadhara Samhita (with Dipika Hindi commentary)*. 1st ed. Edited by Brahmanand Tripathi. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan; 2016. Madhyama Khanda, Chapter 7, Verse 12–15. p. 153.
10. Smita lokhande et al. Efficacy of Panchatikta ghrīt guggul in the management of Mandal kushtha with special reference to psoriasis. *International Journal of Research in Ayurveda and Pharmacy*, September 2016.
11. Vagbhata. *Aṣṭāṅgahṛdayasaṃhitā* (Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaya) Sutrasthana [Sanskrit text with Hindi commentary]. Edited by Brahmanand Tripathi. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan, 2022; Chapter 15 verse 15.
12. Prajakta Bhausahab Jadhav, Suryakiran Wagh, Suryakiran Wagh. Ayurvedic management of Dadru Kushta – A case report. *World J Pharm Res*, 2022; 11(16): 1162–1168.

13. Saha S, Ghosh S. *Tinospora cordifolia*: One plant, many roles. *Anc Sci Life*, 2012; 31(4): 151-159. doi:10.4103/0257-7941.107344
14. *Rasa Tantra Sara Va Siddha Proyoga Sangraha*: Vol.-1, Krishna Gopal Ayurveda Bhavan, Kaleda, Ajmer, 15th edition, 2001; 283-284.